

Evaluating Perceptions of Substance Use Disorder Among Emergency Nurses

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Problem

Substance Use Disorder (SUD)

- Chronic and progressive disease that includes a spectrum of alcohol and/or drug use, from abuse to dependence

Impact

- \$740 billion in costs for treatment, crime, and lost productivity.
- Five-fold increase in overdose-related deaths since 1999
- 115 fatal overdoses per day
- 6 – 20% of RNs have SUD
- Jeopardizes patient care

Purpose

Explore RN perceptions of SUD among RNs in a 24-bed ED

Methods

- Hospital/University IRB Approval
- Anonymous Survey consisting of select all and free-write format
- Descriptive and Inferential Data Analysis

Theoretical Framework

Based on adaptation of Lewin's Change Theory

Results

Respondents:

- 27 anonymous Registered Nurses (66% response rate)
- 74% were female respondents in full-time Emergency Department employment
- 48% had 0 – 5 years of experience in the Emergency Department
- Even distribution of respondents across all shifts

Data Analysis:

- 29.6% (n = 8) participants correctly identified the estimated prevalence of SUD
- 30% of participants could not identify an impaired colleague
- Participants were unclear about consequences for those they reported
- Those who self-identified as capable of identifying an impaired coworker were able to correctly identify observable behaviors ($\chi^2(1) = 4.89, p = .027$)
- FT nurses were less able to identify risk factors for SUD than PT and PD nurses ($\chi^2(1) = 7.56, p = .006$)

Limitations

Limited generalization:

- Small sample size
- Single ED in community hospital
- Write-in responses subject to potential researcher interpretation bias; eliminated in final analysis

Conclusion

- Participants did not know the prevalence of SUD among RNs
- FT nurses were less able to identify risk factors for SUD than PT nurses
- 30% of participants could not identify an impaired colleague
- Participants were unclear about consequences for those reported with suspected impairment

Recommendations

- Implement mandatory SUD education among hospital nurses
- Re-evaluate impact of SUD education through post-test answers and utilization of confidential reporting channels
- SUD education should be added to nursing programs
- Additional SUD research is needed

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